

The Comparative study of Savoring among Arts & Science Post Graduate Students

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Abstract: Savoring has been part of positive psychology, is contextualized reaction toward the experience of positive events. It is a special form of perceived control over positive emotions. This study aimed to understand and analyze savoring of post-graduation students of arts and science background and also to identify the effect of the demographic variables on the savoring. To study the same, total sample of 120 Science and Arts students consisting of male and female samples were included in the study. To measure their savoring levels constructed by Fred Bryant was administered for the subjects. For the obtained raw score, mean and SD was calculated in each groups. Later independent ‘t’ test was carried out to find the difference between the comparative groups. The main finding of the present study reveals that there is no significant difference between arts and science students on savoring. But there is significant difference in savoring between Arts and Science students and there is significant difference in savoring between Arts female and Science female students.

Keywords: Positive experience, Pleasure, Anticipation, Savoring the moment, reminiscence, meta-awareness, well-being, The SBI.

1. INTRODUCTION

Savoring, within the framework of positive psychology, has been defined as “a distinct form of perceived control over positive emotions,” whereby, an individual is capable of “generating, intensifying, and prolonging enjoyment through one’s own volition” (Bryant, 2003, p. 176). Additionally, savoring has been proposed to function as both a trait and a state (Bryant & Veroff, 2007), with trait savoring being a stable personality trait that elicits a predisposed response to a positive experience, and state savoring being a contextualized reaction toward the experience of positive events (Jose, Lim, & Bryant, 2012).

Bryant and Veroff (2007) were the first to highlight explicitly a key conceptual component of savoring that must be always be present in order for savoring to exist— namely, a deliberate attentional focus on ongoing positive feelings. As Bryant and Veroff (2007) put it, “in savoring, people partially set a positive experience apart from their immediately attending self, such that the attending self, interacts more directly with the focused experience” (p. 12). Thus, savoring must involve a mindful meta-awareness of positive experience (see Bryant and Smith, 2015), or else it is simply pleasurable enjoyment (Smith et al., 2014).

Concerning savoring as the management of positive experience, Bryant initially considered savoring to be a form of secondary-positive control over positive feelings that may stem from “beliefs about: cognitive or behavioral strategies that one can use to amplify or prolong enjoyment of positive events, one’s ability to anticipate future positive outcomes in ways that promote a sense of pleasure in the present, one’s ability to recall past positive events in ways that enhance present well-being, friends or relatives who can help one enjoy positive events, even if one cannot do so alone” (Bryant, 1989, pp. 775-776).

The Savoring Beliefs Inventory:

Encouraged by this evidence that people make global self-evaluations of their capacity to savor positive feelings, next step was to refine the broad concept of perceived savoring capacity to include a finer-grained focus on temporal aspects of savoring positive experience. In particular, Bryant hypothesized that people make separate but correlated self-assessments of their ability to savor:

- (a) future positive events before they occur (anticipation)
- (b) present positive events while they are unfolding (savoring the moment)
- (c) past positive events after they occur (reminiscence)—all three of which are essential components of the fundamental human capacity to attend to and appreciate positive experience.

Over the past two decades, the SBI has frequently been used in positive psychology. As cross-cultural research on savoring has grown, international researchers have translated and validated the SBI in a variety of languages, including French (Golay et al., 2018), Spanish (Robles et al., 2011), Romanian (Căzănescu et al., 2019), Chinese (Lin et al., 2011), Japanese (Kawakubo et al., 2019), Korean (Kim and Bryant, 2017), Persian (Aghaie et al., 2017), and Turkish (Metin-Orta, 2018). Bryant and Veroff (2007) also reported the development and validation of the Children's Savoring Beliefs Inventory that is appropriate for respondents with at least a fifth-grade reading level. A large body of research supports the reliability and validity of the SBI as a measure of savoring capacity (Smith and Bryant, 2017). In addition, systematic scrutiny of the individual SBI items strongly supports the instrument's content validity (Kawakubo et al., 2019).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Chen and Zhou (2017) examined the relationships among savoring, positive life events, and hopelessness depression. Participants comprised 266 Chinese undergraduate college students who filled out 3 measures to assess savoring, positive life events, and hopelessness depression. Results showed that savoring was negatively correlated with hopelessness depression and positively correlated with positive life events, and that savoring significantly moderated the relationship between positive life events and hopelessness depression. These findings indicate that savoring is a protective factor for hopelessness depression. Daniel Hurley and Paul Kwon (2012) conducted research on increase savouring the Moment: Differential Impact on Positive and Negative Outcomes. This study tested a group savoring the moment intervention to increase positive outcomes and decrease negative outcomes over 2 weeks. The sample consisted of 193 undergraduate students who completed both sessions (94 interventions and 99 control condition). The intervention group experienced significant decreases in self-reported depressive symptoms and negative affect when compared to the control group. However, positive affect did not differ between the groups.

Sen-Chi Yu et al., (2020) conducted research on using social network sites to boost savoring. They have demonstrated that positive interventions (PIs) can be effective in enhancing well-being. Their study used Face book to conduct a PI based on savoring. Sixty-one university students in Taiwan were randomly assigned to undergo a three-week savoring PI, and 61 participants were assigned to a no-treatment control group. The results showed significantly enhanced positive affect in the treatment group compared to the control group, in both a post-test and a final follow-up, but no significant differences between the two groups in negative affect. The treatment group also displayed significantly lower depression in the post-test, which was not maintained at the follow-up. These results indicate that, for university students, a savoring intervention via Facebook can be an effective way of enhancing positive emotions. Klibert, Amy Luna and Matthew Miceli (2018) examined the effects of "savoring the moment" (the ability to generate, maintain, and extend positive emotions) on the relationship between negative emotions and suicidal behavior in a sample of gender and sexual minorities (GSM). Savoring the moment moderated the associated effects of negative emotions on suicidal behavior; the relationship between negative emotions and suicidal behaviors ceased at higher levels of savoring the moment. Their finding offers preliminary evidence for savoring as a buffer to suicide among subpopulations of GSM individuals.

Lambert D'raven et al., (2015) studied to determine whether positive psychological interventions (PPIs) in a primary health care setting would improve physical and mental health over time. Of the 124 patients who enrolled in this pilot study, 75 completed the six-week program, and 35 participated in two follow-up assessments. Among the participants who remained for all follow-up assessments, scores improved from baseline to 6-month follow-up for health, vitality, mental health, and the effects of mental and physical health on daily activities. This subset of patients reported greater energy and more daily

accomplishments, along with reductions in functional limitations. Improvements in mental and physical health and functioning were shown over a six-month period.

3. METHODOLOGY

Objectives:

1. To investigate whether Arts and Science Post-Graduate students differ significantly in Savoring.
2. To assess Male and Female Post-Graduate students differ significantly in Savoring.

Hypotheses:

- Arts and Science PG students differ significantly in their Savouring.
- PG Male and Female students differ significantly from each other in their Savouring

Variables:

1. Independent Variable: Science and Arts stream of education
2. Dependent Variable: Savoring

Sample:

In order to examine the above-mentioned hypotheses, a total sample of 120 post-graduate students from Arts (60) and Science (60) faculty were selected from Karnatak University, Dharwad. The sample from each faculty consists of 30 male and 30 female PG students. The age range of sample is 21 to 25. Purposive sampling method was adopted to select the sample.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. The students included were of the age group of 21 to 25.
2. PG students were included from only arts and science faculty.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. The students below the age group of 21 and above the age group of 25 were not included as the sample for study.
2. Other faculty apart from arts and science were not included.

Measures used:

Savoring Scale:

The Savoring Bryant Inventory (SBI) Scale was used to measure Savoring of the subjects. A self-report measure designed to assess core characteristics of Savoring. The scale consists of 24 items. With this measure, respondents use a 7-point Likert-type scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree) to rate their level of agreement with 12 positively worded and 12 negatively worded statements, in order to indicate how capable, they believe they are of appreciating positive experiences through anticipating (8 items), savoring the moment (8 items), and reminiscing (8 items). The SBI provides not only separate subscale scores for Anticipating, Savoring the Moment, and Reminiscing, but also a global Total Score, as measures of people's perceived capacity to appreciate positive experience. The Total Score of the SBI showed very good internal consistency (Cronbach Alpha between 0.68 and 0.89). Three week test-retest correlations indicated strong temporal reliability ($r = .84$). The SBI total score correlated positively with various variables indicating good convergent validity, i.e. affect intensity ($r = 0.48$), optimism ($r = 0.50$), extraversion ($r = 0.42$) and happiness intensity ($r = 0.48$).

Statistical Techniques Applied:

- Descriptive statistics (Mean and SD)
- 't' test was carried out to find out the significant difference between male and female PG students.

4. RESULTS

Table 01: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts and Science students on different dimensions of Savoring.

Variable	Scores	Sample Groups		't' value	Significance
		Arts students (60)	Science students (60)		
Anticipating	Mean	46.62	53.38	3.918**	.001
	SD	9.02	9.85		
Savoring the moment	Mean	48.25	51.75	1.940*	.055
	SD	10.31	9.44		
Reminiscing	Mean	49.47	50.53	.583	.561
	SD	10.29	9.76		

*= Significant at 0.05 level

***= Significant at 0.001 level

Table 02: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts male and Science male students on different dimensions of Savoring.

Variable	Scores	Sample Groups		't' value	Significance
		Arts male students (30)	Science male students (30)		
Anticipating	Mean	47.63	57.10	4.35***	.000
	SD	8.78	8.06		
Savoring the moment	Mean	51.23	53.97	0.92	.362
	SD	11.76	11.29		
Reminiscing	Mean	51.12	49.83	-0.42	.675
	SD	11.51	12.23		

***= Significant at 0.001 level

Table 03: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts female and Science female students on different dimensions of Savoring.

Variable	Scores	Sample Groups		't' value	Significance
		Arts female students (30)	Science female students (30)		
Anticipating	Mean	45.61	49.66	1.61	.113
	SD	9.29	10.2		
Savoring the moment	Mean	45.27	49.53	2.30*	.025
	SD	7.72	6.62		
Reminiscing	Mean	47.81	51.24	1.71	.092
	SD	8.78	6.58		

*= Significant at 0.05 level

Table 04: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts male and female students on different dimensions of Savoring.

Variable	Scores	Sample Groups		't' value	Significance
		Arts male students (30)	Arts female students (30)		
Anticipating	Mean	47.63	45.61	0.87	.388
	SD	8.78	9.29		
Savoring the moment	Mean	51.23	45.27	2.32*	.024
	SD	11.76	7.72		
Reminiscing	Mean	51.12	47.81	1.25	.215
	SD	11.51	8.78		

*= Significant at 0.05 level

Table 05: Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Science male and female students on different dimensions of Savoring.

Variable	Scores	Sample Groups		't' value	Significance
		Science male students (30)	Science female students (30)		
Anticipating	Mean	57.1	49.66	3.13***	.003
	SD	8.06	10.2		
Savoring the moment	Mean	53.97	49.53	1.86	.070
	SD	11.29	6.62		
Reminiscing	Mean	49.83	51.24	-0.56	.581
	SD	12.23	6.58		

***= Significant at 0.001 level

5. DISCUSSION

Data was collected from PG Arts and Science students studying in Karnatak University, Dharwad. With a permission of the chairperson the students were contacted and a good rapport was established. After introducing the study to the students, their consent was sought and the research was carried out assuring confidentiality. Socio-demographic information was collected and then the above-mentioned measures were administered with appropriate instructions. The forms were collected after the completion of all the scales. Statistical techniques were applied in the study using Descriptive statistics (Mean and SD) and 't' test. 't' test was carried out to find out the significant difference between male and female PG students.

Table No. 01 shows Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts and Science students on Savoring. On the first dimension anticipating, Science students have higher mean score (53.38) than Arts students (46.62). The obtained 't' value is 3.91, which is highly significant at 0.001 level. This indicates that Science students have high anticipating trait related to savoring than Arts students. On the second dimension savoring the moment, Science students have higher mean score (51.75) than Arts students (48.25). The obtained 't' value is 1.94, which is significant at 0.05 level. This indicates that Science students have high savoring the moment trait than Arts students. On the third dimension reminiscing, Science students have higher mean score (50.53) than Arts students (49.47). The obtained 't' value is 0.583, which is not significant. This shows that there is no significant difference in reminiscing trait related to savoring between Science and Arts students.

Table No. 02 shows Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts Male and Science Male students on Savoring. On the first dimension anticipating, Science male students have higher mean score (57.10) than Arts male students (47.63). The obtained 't' value is 4.35, which is highly significant at 0.000 level. This indicates that Science male students have high anticipating trait related to savoring than Arts male students. On the second dimension savoring the moment, Science male students have higher mean score (53.97) than Arts male students (51.23). The obtained 't' value is 0.92, which is not significant. This indicates that there is no significant difference in savoring the moment trait between Science male students and Arts male students. On the third dimension reminiscing, Arts male students have higher mean score (51.12) than Science male students (49.83). The obtained 't' value is -0.42, which is not significant. This shows that there is no significant difference in reminiscing trait related to savoring between Science male students and Arts male students.

Table No. 03 shows Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts female and Science female students on Savoring. On the first dimension anticipating, Science female students have higher mean score (49.66) than Arts female students (45.61). The obtained 't' value is 1.61, which is not significant. This indicates that there is no significant difference anticipating trait between Science female students and Arts female students. On the second dimension savoring the moment, Science female students have higher mean score (49.53) than Arts female students (45.27). The obtained 't' value is 2.30, which is significant at 0.25 level. This indicates that Science female students have high savoring the moment trait related to savoring than Arts female students. On the third dimension reminiscing, Science male students have higher mean score (51.24) than Arts female students (47.81). The obtained 't' value is 0.92, which is not significant. This shows that there is no significant difference in reminiscing trait related to savoring between Science female students and Arts female students.

Table No. 04 represents Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Arts male and Arts female students on Savoring. On the first dimension anticipating, Arts male students have higher mean score (47.63) than Arts female students (45.61). The obtained 't' value is 0.87, which is not significant. This indicates that there is no significant difference anticipating trait

between Arts male students and Arts female students. On the second dimension savoring the moment, Arts male students have higher mean score (51.23) than Arts female students (45.27). The obtained 't' value is 2.32, which is significant at 0.24 level. This indicates that Arts male students have high savoring the moment trait related to savoring than Arts female students. On the third dimension reminiscing, Arts male students have higher mean score (51.12) than Arts female students (47.81). The obtained 't' value is 1.25, which is not significant. This shows that there is no significant difference in reminiscing trait related to savoring between Arts male students and Arts female students.

Table No. 05 depicts Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' value of Science male and Science female students on Savoring. On the first dimension anticipating, Science male students have higher mean score (57.1) than Science female students (49.66). The obtained 't' value is 3.13, which is highly significant at 0.001 level. This indicates that Science male students have high anticipating trait related to savoring than Science female students. On the second dimension savoring the moment, Science male students have higher mean score (53.97) than Science female students (49.53). The obtained 't' value is 1.86, which is not significant. there is no significant difference in savoring the moment trait related to savoring between Science male students and Science female students. On the third dimension reminiscing, Science female students have higher mean score (51.24) than Science male students (49.83). The obtained 't' value is -0.56, which is not significant. This shows that there is no significant difference in reminiscing trait related to savoring between Science male students and Science female students.

6. CONCLUSION

The main finding of the present study reveals that there is no significant difference between arts and science students on savoring.

- There is significant difference in savoring between Arts and Science students. Science students have high savoring than Arts students.
- There is no significant difference in savoring between Arts male and Science male students.
- There is significant difference in savoring between Arts female and Science female students. Science female students have high savoring than Arts female students.
- There is no significant difference in savoring between Arts male and Arts female students.
- There is no significant difference in savoring between Science male and Science female students.

Limitations of the Study:

- The sample size in the main group and sub groups are smaller. The result cannot be generalized.
- Other socio-demographic variables were not taken into consideration in the study, they may have implications on the dependent variables.
- The tools were not administered individually, which may lead to errors in the responses given by the subjects.

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